

Supplementary Appendix for "Application Component Placement and Resource Optimization in Computing Continua"

Hamta Sedghani, Mauro Passacantando, Danilo Ardagna

INTRODUCTION

This document provides supplementary material for the paper "Application Component Placement and Resource Optimization in Computing Continua", submitted in *IEEE Transactions on Service Computing*. Only supporting materials are included here; the main text is omitted in accordance with IEEE copyright policy.

In the following subsections, we present the theorem proofs, the experimental setup tables, and the results for components and paths response times, edge energy consumption, and the ANCOVA test.

Proofs of the theorems

We provide the proofs of the theorems stated in Sections 4, 5 and 6, and we outline the idea behind the correctness of Algorithm 1. We recall that Theorems 4.1 and 5.1 state the non-convexity of constraints (P1g) in problem (P1) and convexity of problem (P2), respectively. Theorem 6.1 investigates all possible conditions related to the global constraint P and if the problem is feasible, it provides an optimal number of additional instances across all layers for a specific resource partitioning.

Proof of Theorem 4.1

Proof. Recall that the global constraint (P1g) has a term that contains the product of two binary decision variables:

$$f(x) = \sum_{\substack{i,k \in P: \\ i \neq k}} \frac{\delta_{ik}}{g(x)}, \quad \text{where } g(x) = \sum_{\substack{j,l \in \mathcal{J}, \\ j \neq l}} B_{jl} x_{ij} x_{kl}.$$

The first order partial derivatives of f with respect to the variables x_{ij} are

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_{ij}} = \sum_{\substack{i,k \in P: \\ i \neq k}} -\delta_{ik} \frac{1}{g(x)^2} \frac{\partial g(x)}{\partial x_{ij}},$$

where

$$\frac{\partial g(x)}{\partial x_{ij}} = \sum_{\substack{l \in \mathcal{J}, \\ l \neq j}} B_{jl} x_{kl},$$

thus

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_{ij}} = \sum_{\substack{i,k \in P: \\ i \neq k}} -\delta_{ik} \frac{1}{g(x)^2} \sum_{\substack{l \in \mathcal{J}, \\ l \neq j}} B_{jl} x_{kl}$$

- H. Sedghani and D. Ardagna are with Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy. Email: {name.lastname}@polimi.it (Corresponding author: Hamta Sedghani, Email: hamta.sedghani@polimi.it)
- M. Passacantando is with University of Milano-Bicocca, Milan, Italy, Email: mauro.passacantando@unimib.it.

The second order partial derivatives of f are

$$\frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x_{ij} \partial x_{kl}} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_{kl}} \left(\sum_{\substack{i,k \in P: \\ i \neq k}} -\delta_{ik} \frac{1}{g(x)^2} \sum_{\substack{l \in \mathcal{J}, \\ l \neq j}} B_{jl} x_{kl} \right).$$

The first term $\frac{1}{g(x)^2}$ involves $g(x)$, which is the sum of bilinear terms; hence its partial derivative with respect to x_{kl} is

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_{kl}} \left(\frac{1}{g(x)^2} \right) = -2 \frac{1}{g(x)^3} \frac{\partial g(x)}{\partial x_{kl}}.$$

The second term $\sum_{\substack{l \in \mathcal{J}, \\ l \neq j}} B_{jl} x_{kl}$ is linear, so its partial derivative with respect to x_{kl} is

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_{kl}} \left(\sum_{\substack{l \in \mathcal{J}, \\ l \neq j}} B_{jl} x_{kl} \right) = B_{jl}.$$

Therefore, we get

$$\frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x_{ij} \partial x_{kl}} = \sum_{\substack{i,k \in P: \\ i \neq k}} \delta_{ik} \left[\frac{2}{g(x)^3} \sum_{\substack{l \in \mathcal{J}, \\ l \neq j}} B_{jl} x_{kl} \sum_{\substack{m \in \mathcal{J}, \\ m \neq k}} B_{jm} x_{il} - \frac{B_{jl}}{g(x)^2} \right].$$

The Hessian matrix above is indefinite due to the presence of mixed second-order partial derivatives involving products of the decision variables $x_{ij} x_{kl}$. Hence, the global constraint (P1g) is non-convex. \square

Proof of Theorem 5.1

Proof. To prove that problem (P2) is convex, it is sufficient to prove that the function

$$f(n_j) = \frac{n_j}{n_j - L_j}$$

is convex when $n_j > L_j$. The first derivative of f is

$$f'(n_j) = -\frac{L_j}{(n_j - L_j)^2},$$

while the second derivative of f is

$$f''(n_j) = \frac{2L_j}{(n_j - L_j)^3} > 0,$$

thus f is convex. \square

Proof of Theorem 6.1

Proof. We remark that

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P} \frac{(NC_j + n'_j) Z_{Pj}}{NC_j + n'_j - L_j} \geq \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P} \frac{(NC_j + N'_j) Z_{Pj}}{NC_j + N'_j - L_j}$$

Scenario	#Components	#Computational layers	Bimodal trace range λ (req/s)	#Local and global constraints	Activation function	Neurons per layer	#Training iterations
1	5	Edge: 1, Cloud: 2	[25, 85]	3, 3	[ReLU, ReLU]	[256, 128]	600
2	7	Edge: 1, Cloud: 3	[45, 105]	4, 4	[ReLU, ReLU]	[512, 256]	600
3	10	Edge: 2, Cloud: 3	[20, 170]	5, 5	[ReLU, ReLU, ReLU]	[512, 256, 128]	800
4	15	Edge: 3, Cloud: 7	[20, 170]	7, 7	[ReLU, ReLU, ReLU]	[1024, 512, 256]	800

Table 1: Parameters of scalability analysis.

Scenario	Edge layers	Edge power model	Cloud device	PC^{pk}	PC^{id}
1	Raspberry Pi 1B	$P = 0.1220 \times U + 1.3143$	Cloud-1	60	24
			Cloud-2	117	86
2	Raspberry Pi 1B	$P = 0.1220 \times U + 1.3143$	Cloud-1	60	24
			Cloud-2	117	86
			Cloud-3	135	93
3	Raspberry Pi 1B	$P = 0.1220 \times U + 1.3143$	Cloud-1	60	24
	Raspberry Pi 2B	$P = 1.1488 \times U + 1.2903$	Cloud-2	117	86
			Cloud-3	135	93
4	Raspberry Pi 1B	$P = 0.1220 \times U + 1.3143$	Cloud-1	60	24
	Raspberry Pi 2B	$P = 1.1488 \times U + 1.2903$	Cloud-2	117	86
			Cloud-3	135	93
			Cloud-4	117	75
	Raspberry Pi 4B	$P = 3.4842 \times U + 2.2434$	Cloud-5	169	105
			Cloud-6	276	164
			Cloud-7	352	216

 Table 2: Edge and cloud devices per scenario with corresponding linear power-consumption models. The edge power model is adapted from [1], and the parameters PC^{pk} and PC^{id} (see the linear model in (14)) are derived from [2].

holds for any $n'_j \in [0, N'_j]$. Hence, if $\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P} \frac{(NC_j + N'_j)Z_{Pj}}{NC_j + N'_j - L_j} > TH_P$ holds, then constraint (P3b) cannot be satisfied and problem (P3) is infeasible.

Problem (P3) is convex because its objective function is linear and constraint (P3b) is convex. Moreover, it admits an optimal solution and the Slater constraint qualification holds. Hence, problem (P3) is equivalent to solve the corresponding KKT system:

$$\begin{aligned}
 c_j - \mu \frac{L_j Z_{Pj}}{(NC_j + n'_j - L_j)^2} - \nu_j + \delta_j &= 0 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_P \\
 \mu \left[\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} \frac{(NC_j + n'_j)Z_{Pj}}{NC_j + n'_j - L_j} - TH_P \right] &= 0 \\
 \nu_j n'_j &= 0 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_P \\
 \delta_j (N'_j - n'_j) &= 0 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_P \\
 \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} \frac{(NC_j + n'_j)Z_{Pj}}{NC_j + n'_j - L_j} &\leq TH_P \\
 0 \leq n'_j \leq N'_j &\quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_P \\
 \mu \geq 0, \nu_j \geq 0, \delta_j \geq 0 &\quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_P
 \end{aligned}$$

If

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P} \frac{NC_j Z_{Pj}}{NC_j - L_j} \leq TH_P,$$

then the optimal solution is $n_j^{I*} = 0$ for all $j \in \mathcal{J}_P$, with $\mu = \delta_j = 0$ and $\nu_j = c_j$ for any $j \in \mathcal{J}_P$.

If

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P} \frac{NC_j Z_{Pj}}{NC_j - L_j} > TH_P,$$

then $\mu > 0$. We define the following subsets of indices related to the optimal solution n^{I*} :

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{J}_P^0 &:= \{j \in \mathcal{J}_P : n_j^{I*} = 0\}, \\
 \mathcal{J}_P^> &:= \{j \in \mathcal{J}_P : 0 < n_j^{I*} < N'_j\}, \\
 \mathcal{J}_P^- &:= \{j \in \mathcal{J}_P : n_j^{I*} = N'_j\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

For any $j \in \mathcal{J}_P^0$, one has $n_j^{I*} = 0$, $\delta_j = 0$ and $\nu_j \geq 0$, hence

$$\sqrt{\mu} \leq \frac{NC_j - L_j}{\sqrt{L_j Z_{Pj}/c_j}}. \quad (1)$$

For any $j \in \mathcal{J}_P^>$ we have $\nu_j = \delta_j = 0$, hence

$$n_j^{I*} = L_j - NC_j + \sqrt{\mu} \sqrt{L_j Z_{Pj}/c_j}. \quad (2)$$

Moreover, $0 < n_j^{I*} < N'_j$ implies

$$\frac{NC_j - L_j}{\sqrt{L_j Z_{Pj}/c_j}} < \sqrt{\mu} < \frac{NC_j + N'_j - L_j}{\sqrt{L_j Z_{Pj}/c_j}}. \quad (3)$$

For any $j \in \mathcal{J}_P^-$, one has $n_j^{I*} = N'_j$, $\nu_j = 0$ and $\delta_j \geq 0$, hence

$$\sqrt{\mu} \geq \frac{NC_j + N'_j - L_j}{\sqrt{L_j Z_{Pj}/c_j}}. \quad (4)$$

Since $\mu > 0$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 TH_P &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P} \frac{(NC_j + n'_j)Z_{Pj}}{NC_j + n'_j - L_j} \\
 &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P^>} \frac{L_j + \sqrt{\mu} \sqrt{L_j Z_{Pj}/c_j}}{\sqrt{\mu} \sqrt{L_j Z_{Pj}/c_j}} Z_{Pj} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P^0} \frac{NC_j Z_{Pj}}{NC_j - L_j} \\
 &\quad + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P^-} \frac{(NC_j + N'_j)Z_{Pj}}{NC_j + N'_j - L_j} \\
 &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P^>} Z_{Pj} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mu}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P^>} \sqrt{L_j Z_{Pj} c_j} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P^0} \frac{NC_j Z_{Pj}}{NC_j - L_j} \\
 &\quad + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P^-} \frac{(NC_j + N'_j)Z_{Pj}}{NC_j + N'_j - L_j}
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\sqrt{\mu} = \frac{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P^>} \sqrt{L_j Z_{Pj} c_j}}{TH_P - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P^0} Z_{Pj} - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P^-} \frac{NC_j Z_{Pj}}{NC_j - L_j} - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_P^-} \frac{(NC_j + N'_j)Z_{Pj}}{NC_j + N'_j - L_j}} := \alpha.$$

The definition of the sets \mathcal{J}_P^0 , $\mathcal{J}_P^>$, \mathcal{J}_P^- and (2) imply that the optimal solution n^{I*} is given by formula (20). Finally, (1), (3) and (4) guarantee that α satisfies conditions (22)–(24) (in the main content). \square

Optimality of Algorithm 1

The conditions (22)–(24) in Theorem 6.1 guarantee that the indices corresponding to the highest values of β_j belong

to the set \mathcal{J}_P^0 , the indices corresponding to the lowest values of γ_j belong to the set \mathcal{J}_P^- , while the remaining indices belong to $\mathcal{J}_P^>$. For this reason, in Algorithm 1 we set \mathcal{J}_P^- equal to the set of indices corresponding to the h smallest values of γ_j (with $h \in \{0, \dots, |\mathcal{J}_P|\}$), \mathcal{J}_P^0 equal to the set of indices corresponding to the k highest values of β_j (with $k \in \{0, \dots, |\mathcal{J}_P|\}$), and $\mathcal{J}_P^>$ equal to the set of remaining indices. Since the optimal partition exists, the double for loop in Algorithm 1 allows finding it after at most $O(|\mathcal{J}_P|^2)$ iterations. Figure 1 shows an example of the optimal partition $\{\mathcal{J}_P^0, \mathcal{J}_P^>, \mathcal{J}_P^-\}$ based on the position of α with respect to the values of β_j and γ_j .

Figure 1: Example of optimal partition $\{\mathcal{J}_P^0, \mathcal{J}_P^>, \mathcal{J}_P^-\}$.

System Parameters	
$ \mathcal{I} $	{5, 7, 10, 15}
D_{ij}	Uniform distribution in [0.1, 0.5] s
c_j	Uniform distribution in [0.5, 1] \$/h
N_j	Uniform distribution in [50, 100]
Agent Parameters	
Episode length	360 steps
lr	decaying from 0.01 to 0.001 during 3000000 steps
γ	0.1
β	0.7
$train_batch_size$	4096
$sgd_minibatch_size$	512

Table 3: Simulation parameters

Experimental setup parameters

Table 1 and Table 2 present the detailed system specifications used in the scalability analysis and the power consumption parameters, while Table 3 summarizes the key parameters employed in the numerical analyses.

Comparison of component and path response times: CF vs. BARON

Figures 2a and 2b show the response times (RT) of components and paths for a single instance of a small system with four components and two resources (see Section 8.2), obtained using the KKT-based closed-form solution (CF) and BARON, respectively, along with their corresponding thresholds. The results demonstrate near-identical behavior, with response times virtually identical between the two methods.

Edge energy consumption

This section analyzes the edge-only energy consumption across all methods. As shown in Figure 3a, the comparison among our approach, BARON [3], and SPACE4AI-D [4] (corresponding to the experiments in Section 8.3.1) reveals greater variability among all methods. Since this metric is not explicitly optimized, the differences arise from placement decisions driven by the total energy objective (which is proportional to the total cost) and by the need to offload edge layers that become bottlenecks under higher loads. Nevertheless, PPO_AB often consumes less edge energy than competitors, further confirming the efficiency of its resource allocation policy. Finally, the disconnected lines correspond to cases where a method failed to find feasible solutions in any of the five random instances, reflecting their

(a) Response Time (RT) of LCs and GCs by (b) Response Time (RT) of LCs and GCs by solver
Figure 2: Comparison of KKT-based closed form (CF) and BARON, single instance of a small system with four components and two resources.

scalability limitations.

Similarly, Figure 3b compares our approach with PPO_DLX [5] and min_k_cut (corresponding to the experiments in Section 8.3.2). The min_k_cut method shows the highest edge energy consumption, as its focus on minimizing communication overhead places more components on edge layers, increasing the number of active instances and thus overall energy usage. However, it fails under peak workload conditions in all scenarios, as assigning more components to the edge prevents it from satisfying the QoS constraints.

Statistical Analysis

To evaluate the effectiveness of PPO_AB in minimizing operational costs, we conducted a statistical comparison against four baseline methods: BARON, SPACE4AI-D, PPO_DLX and min_k_cut. The analysis was performed across four representative scenarios characterized by increasing system complexity (5, 7, 10, and 15 components and five random instances for each scenario as mentioned in Section 8.1). Figure 4a illustrates the cost difference between PPO_AB and the two baselines, BARON, SPACE4AI-D, across workloads for each scenario. Each line represents the mean cost difference over five instances, with the shaded region indicating the standard deviation. Positive values indicate that PPO_AB outperformed the respective method. Notably, the shaded regions are narrower in the more complex scenarios (10 and 15 components), particularly at higher workload levels. This reduction in shading does not indicate lower variability but is instead due to a decrease in the number of available data points. Specifically, instances where a baseline method failed to produce a feasible solution were excluded from the analysis. For example, in the 15-component scenario, SPACE4AI-D was unable to find feasible solutions for any instances with workloads above 147, resulting in an early termination of its cost curve. Markers in the plots denote workload levels at which a method failed to find feasible solutions in at least four out of five instances. Figure 4b illustrates the cost difference between PPO_AB and two additional baseline methods, PPO_DLX and min_k_cut, across varying workload levels for each scenario. As system complexity increases, both PPO_DLX and min_k_cut exhibit a growing number of infeasible cases, especially under high workloads. These frequent infeasibilities, particularly visible for min_k_cut in the 15-component scenario (where PPO_DLX is omitted due to its prohibitively large action space, which renders it inapplicable), underscore the limitations of these baselines in maintaining QoS constraints, whereas PPO_AB consistently produces feasible and cost-effective solutions.

To quantify the statistical significance of these differences, we performed a *robust ANCOVA* (Analysis of Co-

Figure 3: Edge energy consumption among our full framework, BARON, SPACE4AI-D, PPO_DLX and min_k_cut average of 5 random instances.

Figure 4: Cost difference ($OtherMethod - PPO_{AB}$) across workloads. Lines show the mean over 5 instances, shaded areas indicate standard deviation. Markers highlight workloads where the methods failed to find a feasible solution in at least 4 out of 5 instances.

variance) test [6], treating workload as a covariate. Robust ANCOVA estimates the difference in average cost between methods across varying workload thresholds, reporting both confidence intervals (CIs) and corresponding p -values. A CI, such as $[a, b]$ with a p -value of 0.01, implies that there is a 99% level of confidence that the true cost difference lies within that range. Crucially, when the CI excludes zero—particularly at conventional significance levels (e.g., $p < 0.05$ or $p < 0.01$)—this indicates a statistically significant difference in performance between the methods being compared.

The results are summarized in Table 4 and Table 5, which report the estimated cost difference between PPO_AB and each baseline at five systematically chosen representative workload levels. These points are selected internally by the WRS2 package to summarize the covariate (in this case, Workload) and facilitate interpretation. The tables also report the corresponding confidence intervals and p -values. In Table 4, the ANCOVA results confirm that PPO_AB consistently achieves lower or competitive costs compared

to BARON and SPACE4AI-D. For the most complex scenario (15 components), the differences are not only larger but also statistically significant across all workload levels ($p_value < 0.001$). In simpler scenarios (7 and 10 components), PPO_AB performs comparably to SPACE4AI-D, with differences becoming significant in the higher workload ranges. Against BARON, PPO_AB outperforms even in low-complexity settings (7 and 10 components). These results demonstrate the robustness and scalability of PPO_AB, particularly in scenarios where traditional optimization methods struggle to find feasible or cost-effective solutions.

Table 5 presents a detailed statistical analysis of the cost differences between PPO_AB and the two baselines, PPO_DLX and min_k_cut. Although PPO_AB consistently achieves lower costs than PPO_DLX and min_k_cut across all scenarios (as indicated by the positive Diff values), the differences are not always statistically significant according to the ANCOVA test. This can be attributed to two factors. First, the assumption of homogeneous resources with identical costs across all layers—necessitated by the

Scenario	λ [req/s]	vs BARON			vs SPACE4AI-D		
		Diff	CI	p-value	Diff	CI	p-value
5 Comps	25.28	-1.0449	[-2.2522, 0.1624]	0.0263	-0.5893	[-1.8452, 0.6667]	0.2281
	30.21	-1.0798	[-2.5185, 0.3588]	0.0539	-0.5657	[-2.0326, 0.9012]	0.3218
	43.42	-1.0092	[-2.8078, 0.7893]	0.1494	-0.3102	[-2.1477, 1.5272]	0.6644
	57.48	-0.9090	[-3.3127, 1.4947]	0.3313	0.1304	[-2.3640, 2.6248]	0.8931
	84.08	-2.4320	[-7.5582, 2.6941]	0.2234	-0.8288	[-6.0628, 4.4052]	0.6842
7 Comps	45.31	4.3040	[2.9290, 5.6789]	0.0000	1.6518	[0.5000, 2.8036]	0.0002
	51.35	5.0379	[3.3083, 6.7675]	0.0000	1.5887	[0.1554, 3.0219]	0.0045
	63.53	6.4227	[4.2770, 8.5684]	0.0000	2.1264	[0.2715, 3.9812]	0.0033
	78.10	9.9806	[6.5130, 13.4482]	0.0000	4.6482	[1.9023, 7.3941]	0.0000
	103.94	43.7517	[33.3007, 54.2026]	0.0000	5.5943	[0.2534, 10.9353]	0.0075
10 Comps	20.64	8.9085	[4.3870, 13.4299]	0.0000	2.9190	[-0.9622, 6.8002]	0.0535
	31.84	11.8843	[6.2591, 17.5095]	0.0000	3.4593	[-1.1473, 8.0659]	0.0538
	65.81	16.4093	[8.8757, 23.9429]	0.0000	4.3530	[-1.6157, 10.3216]	0.0611
	100.55	43.3407	[29.3800, 57.3014]	0.0000	9.7334	[2.3599, 17.1070]	0.0007
	168.02	35.0044	[18.8584, 51.1505]	0.0000	31.5321	[16.2192, 46.8449]	0.0000
15 Comps	20.64	263.1518	[227.5357, 298.7680]	0.0000	31.3049	[26.5777, 36.0322]	0.0000
	31.84	255.0906	[222.9551, 287.2261]	0.0000	36.0979	[30.2831, 41.9128]	0.0000
	65.81	238.3058	[210.8436, 265.7679]	0.0000	45.7484	[38.3317, 53.1650]	0.0000
	100.55	207.6311	[176.1996, 239.0627]	0.0000	107.8733	[89.4390, 126.3075]	0.0000
	168.02	288.4801	[254.5853, 322.3748]	0.0000	240.6555	[235.3294, 245.9815]	0.0000

Table 4: ANCOVA results comparing PPO_AB vs BARON and SPACE4AI-D across scenarios. Differences represent the cost of comparator minus the cost of PPO_AB.

Scenario	λ [req/s]	vs PPO_DLX			vs min_k_cut		
		Diff	CI	p-value	Diff	CI	p-value
5 Comps	1.27	0.8537	[-1.2796, 2.9870]	0.3040	0.5033	[-1.6490, 2.6556]	0.5480
	9.02	1.0066	[-1.5890, 3.6023]	0.3191	0.6590	[-1.9307, 3.2487]	0.5133
	31.17	1.2395	[-1.9654, 4.4444]	0.3204	0.9533	[-2.2780, 4.1846]	0.4484
	53.60	1.9389	[-1.6091, 5.4870]	0.1605	16.2284	[10.6286, 21.8283]	0.0000
	98.83	6.9412	[3.3377, 10.5447]	0.0000	9.9421	[7.1890, 12.6952]	0.0000
7 Comps	1.12	1.1827	[-1.4814, 3.8468]	0.2542	0.4523	[-2.2197, 3.1243]	0.6636
	5.82	1.2136	[-2.0682, 4.4954]	0.3421	0.5379	[-2.7578, 3.8336]	0.6750
	18.98	1.2456	[-2.8316, 5.3229]	0.4325	0.6664	[-3.4205, 4.7533]	0.6752
	32.35	1.4139	[-2.6859, 5.1513]	0.3757	1.6147	[-2.9485, 6.1778]	0.3634
	59.30	17.2312	[10.6671, 23.7954]	0.0000	42.7992	[39.8231, 45.7753]	0.0000
10 Comps	1.05	1.7948	[-0.4168, 4.0065]	0.0372	0.7322	[-1.4751, 2.9394]	0.3941
	4.22	1.8080	[-0.8424, 4.4584]	0.0798	0.7938	[-1.8653, 3.4530]	0.4431
	12.89	1.8666	[-1.4527, 5.1859]	0.1486	0.9414	[-2.3817, 4.2645]	0.4667
	21.73	2.7089	[-1.3037, 6.7215]	0.0830	1.3716	[-2.4159, 5.1591]	0.3522
	39.53	43.6529	[35.0983, 52.2075]	0.0000	59.6729	[50.1918, 69.1540]	0.0000
15 Comps	1.05	—	—	—	2.2154	[-4.0022, 8.4330]	0.3600
	4.22	—	—	—	2.2592	[-5.4602, 9.9785]	0.4521
	12.89	—	—	—	2.7635	[-7.0413, 12.5684]	0.4689
	21.73	—	—	—	101.2875	[75.1686, 127.4065]	0.0000
	39.53	—	—	—	176.6480	[165.8421, 187.4539]	0.0000

Table 5: ANCOVA results comparing PPO_AB vs PPO_DLX and min_k_cut across scenarios. Differences represent the cost of comparator minus the cost of PPO_AB.

inability of the alternative methods to handle heterogeneous environments (see Section 8.3.2)—diminishes the influence of component placement decisions, thereby narrowing the cost differentials between methods. Second and most importantly, ANCOVA only considers feasible solutions — that is, solutions that meet the QoS constraints. In contrast, the PPO_DLX and min_k_cut methods often incur substantial QoS violations, particularly in large-scale or high-workload scenarios. These infeasible runs are excluded from the ANCOVA analysis, meaning the comparison is based only on their best-performing (feasible) instances. Consequently, the ANCOVA test underestimates the practical advantage of PPO_AB, which consistently yields feasible solutions with significantly no violations. In real deployment scenarios, where feasibility is essential, PPO_AB demonstrates clear superiority despite conservative statistical significance in some test cases.

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